

The Baal Cycle

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Entry tags: northern Levant, Ancient Mediterranean, Religious Group, Canaanite Religions, Canaanite, Poetry, Ancient Syrian Religion, Ancient Western Asia, Levantine Religion, Syro-Palestinian Religion, Death conceptions, Ancient Western Asia, Phoenician Cult, Semitic, Cosmic domains, Text, Epic, Northwest Semitic, Afro-Asiatic, Excavated text, Calendar, Central Semitic, Near East, West Semitic, Language, Ancient Semitic Text, Ugarito-Phoenician, Ugaritic

The Baal Cycle is a work of narrative poetry written in the Ugaritic language and cuneiform script during the Late Bronze Age. The story features a West Semitic pantheon and centres around the character Baal, a young storm-god who vanquishes the sea-god Yamm, celebrates his ascent to kingship by having a palace built, and sojourns in the realm of the dead before rising again. All of this he accomplishes with the help of a colourful host of other deities, particularly the fearsome goddess Anat. The Baal Cycle stretches across six fragmentary clay tablets. Although much of the text can be plausibly reconstructed on the basis of parallel passages, some of the work is simply lost. The tablets were discovered in the 1930s at the site of Ras Shamra (in modern Syria) in what seems to have been a library or archive of a temple official. The centrality of the storm-god in the Baal Cycle reflects the importance of this deity in the city-state of Ugarit, the acropolis of which featured an impressive temple devoted to him. The battle between a warrior deity and a sea monster (Chaoskampf) appears across ancient West Asian literary traditions (e.g., in the Babylonian Enuma Elish and in the Hebrew Bible), and it is fitting that this detailed elaboration on the motif should come from Ugarit, an urban centre dependent upon maritime trade for its wealth. Although the text makes minimal reference to humans, it is nevertheless infused with ecological, political, and social realities of the (human) inhabitants of Ugarit.

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1350 BCE

Region: Ugarit

Region tags: Southwest Asia, Levant, Eastern Mediterranean

Ugarit in the Late Bronze Age according to written documents and natural geographical boundaries.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Smith, Mark S. "The Baal Cycle." In *Ugaritic Narrative Poetry*, edited by Simon B. Parker. *Writings from the Ancient World* 9. Atlanta: Scholars Press, 1997.
- Source 2: Wyatt, N. *Religious Texts from Ugarit*. 2nd ed. New York: Sheffield Academic, 2002.
- Source 3: Pardee, Dennis. "The Ba'lu Myth." In *Canonical Compositions from the Biblical World*. Vol. 1 of *The Context of Scripture*, edited by William W. Hallo. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

Notes: The above sources present reconstructed versions of the Baal Cycle in English translation (Smith includes Ugaritic transliteration). For the plates (photos of the actual cuneiform tablets), see Mark S. Smith, *The Ugaritic Baal Cycle, Vol. 1: Introduction with Text, Translation & Commentary of KTU 1.1-1.2* (Leiden: Brill, 1994), and Mark S. Smith and Wayne T. Pitard, *The Baal Cycle. Volume II. Introduction with Text, Translation and Commentary of KTU/CAT 1.3-1.4* (Leiden: Brill, 2008). See also M. Dietrich, O. Loretz, and J. Sanmartín, eds. *The Cuneiform Alphabetic Texts from Ugarit, Ras Ibn Hani, and Other Places, KTU: Second, Enlarged Edition, ALASPM 8* (Münster, 1995).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: n/a

– Source 1 Description: n/a

Notes: Unfortunately, no open access translation of the Baal Cycle is currently available online (as of 2024).

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: n/a

– Source 1 Description: n/a

Notes: Unfortunately, no open access transliteration or plates of the Baal Cycle are currently available online (as of 2024).

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Impressed

↳ Tool for making the impression(s)

– Other [specify]: stylus

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Clay

↳ Clay object

– Clay tablet

↳ Type of clay

– Type of clay: n/a

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: alterations at the oral stage of development

Notes: Like so much literature from ancient western Asia, the Baal cycle show some signs of a compositional history at the stage of oral transition.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb

– No

Cemetery

– No

Temple

– Yes

Shrine

– No

Altar

– No

Devotional marker

– No

Cenotaph

– No

- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - I don't know
- ↳ Library/archive
 - Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: n/a

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The tablets of the Baal Cycle were discovered in the same space (adjacent to two temples) as several inscribed bronze tools.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: There is no indication that the Baal Cycle represents canonical scriptures (a concept that belongs to later historical eras). However, the story of the storm god conquering a sea god evidently carried religious and political significance across the West Asia during the second and first millennia BCE.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to

the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: n/a

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: n/a

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: While the Baal Cycle does not formulate a specific calendar, it seems to allude to the annual weather cycle (e.g., with the storm god dying in the heat of the summer and returning to life to bring rain in the fall).

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Whether there is a "supreme high-god" in the Baal Cycle is debatable. There is an older father god (El), who holds some authority over the other gods. However, the text has the young storm-god Baal become king over the land and the other deities.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: There are a few allusions to deceased humans who have become deified and receive offerings, but they play no role in the narrative.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The question on the presence of non-human supernatural beings is a bit awkward to answer, because all of the characters in the Baal Cycle are non-human and most are supernatural (there are a few animals). In fact, there are no human characters in the text.

Supernatural beings can be seen

– I don't know

Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: n/a

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
 - Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: monarchy

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: n/a

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings do not mete out punishment on humans, but they seek to punish one another in the course of their rivalries.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings do not bestow rewards on humans, but they do offer gifts to one another.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: While the Baal Cycle is not typically understood as a messianic text, it might be plausible to understand the highly anticipated return of Baal from death (i.e., the coming of fall rains) as a kind of messianic event.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: While no general social norms are prescribed by the Baal Cycle, the various characters do model social decorum in the course of their interactions with one another (e.g., when it comes to the hospitality, honouring social superiors, delivering messages, etc.).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The Baal cycle does not explicitly advocate any important virtues, though it models some virtues implicitly (e.g., cooperation, courage, ritual adherence, familial piety, etc.).

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The texts seems to have been produced by members of a priestly-scribal elite connected with

the palace (the sixth tablet of the cycle bears a colophon identifying the scribe as Ilimalku, the student of a diviner and high temple official in the service of King Niqmaddu of Ugarit).

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: n/a

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Baal Cycle, Smith, Mark S.. The Ugaritic Baal Cycle, Vol. 1: Introduction with Text, Translation & Commentary of KTU 1.1-1.2. Leiden: Brill, 1994.

Reference: The Baal Cycle, Smith, Mark S., and Wayne T. Pitard. The Baal Cycle. Volume II. Introduction with Text, Translation and Commentary of KTU/CAT 1.3-1.4. Leiden: Brill, 2008.

Reference: The Baal Cycle, Tudendhaft, Aaron. Baal and the Politics of Poetry. Abingdon/New York: Routledge, 2018.

Reference: The Baal Cycle, Smith, Mark S.. "The Baal Cycle". In Ugaritic Narrative Poetry, edited by Simon B. Parker. Writings from the Ancient World 9. Atlanta: Scholars Press, 1997.

Reference: The Baal Cycle, Pardee, Dennis. "The Ba'lu Myth". In Canonical Compositions from the Biblical World. Vol. 1 of the Context of Scripture, edited by William W. Hallo. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

Reference: The Baal Cycle, Dietrich, M., O. Loretz, and J. Sanmartín, eds.. The Cuneiform Alphabetic Texts from Ugarit, Ras Ibn Hani, and Other Places. Edited by M. Dietrich, O. Loretz, and J. Sanmartín. KTU: Second, Enlarged Edition... ALASPM 8. Münster, 1995.

Reference: The Baal Cycle, Yon, Marguerite. The City of Ugarit at Tell Ras Shamra. Eisenbrauns, 2006.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=2YWQZ6x56dAC>.

Reference: The Baal Cycle, Wyatt, N.. Religious Texts from Ugarit.. 2nd ed.. New York: Sheffield Academic, 2002.